

The Impact of Leadership Styles on Employee Retention: A Case Study of High School Teachers in Battambang, Cambodia

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Abstract

The study of leadership styles plays a crucial role in understanding how effective leadership can influence organizational success and employee satisfaction. This study aims to 1) examine the influence of democratic leadership, transformational leadership, and laissez-faire leadership on public organization employees' retention; 2) search for the perceptions of civil servants, comparing male and female staff, regarding the variability of democratic leadership, transformational leadership, laissez-faire leadership, and employee retention; and 3) study the views of civil servants on leadership variability in the three types of leadership styles in public organizations in Battambang Province. The quantitative research method employed questionnaires with 261 civil servants working at ministries, universities, and high schools in Battambang Province. The results revealed that democratic leadership ($\beta = .247$, $T = 2.299$, $P = .022$, $P < 0.05$) and transformational leadership ($\beta = .901$, $T = 8.19$, $P = .000$, $P < .001$) had positive effects on the retention of staff and civil servants. However, laissez-faire leadership harmed the retention of staff and civil servants ($\beta = .165$, $T = 2.465$, $P = .014$, $P < 0.05$). This study concluded that democratic and transformational leadership positively influence employee retention in public organizations in Battambang Province, whereas laissez-faire leadership has a negative impact. Ministries, universities, and institutions should foster democratic and transformational leadership styles through targeted training programs and minimize laissez-faire leadership practices to improve employee retention.

Keywords: *Leadership, Democratic, Transformational, Laissez-faire, High School Teacher*

JEL Classification codes: *M12, I23, O15.*

Suggested citation: Meas, S., Sok, S., Tumvet, V., Sam, R., and Soeurn, C. (2024). The Impact of Leadership Styles on Employee Retention: A Case Study of High School Teachers in Battambang, Cambodia. *European Journal of Management, Economics and Business*, 1(3), 52-62. DOI: 10.59324/ejmeb.2024.1(3).05

Introduction

In leadership, leaders use different styles and approaches, which affect their teams or subordinates. These styles significantly influence the ethical dynamics and overall performance of the group (Bass & Riggio, 2006). According to Michael (2008), leadership theory explains leadership through the qualities and powers leaders use to achieve organizational goals. Leaders are often classified as autocratic, democratic, bureaucratic, charismatic, or laissez-faire on the basis of their leadership

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characteristics (Asianab, 2023). In the Democratic leadership style, the leader is the final decision maker, but team members or staff are also involved in the decision-making process (Harter & Hayes, 2002). In the transformational leadership style, leaders motivate their team with a clear vision and a focus on the future while also communicating and delegating responsibilities to team members (Deci et al., 1989). In the laissez-faire leadership style, leaders allow employees to work independently while regularly monitoring their progress and focusing on experienced or highly skilled staff, although the level of management involvement is often minimal (Chork et al. 2024; Efinger et al., 2004).

Many organizations face challenges in retaining competent staff due to high competition. Retaining skilled employees is crucial because they are the lifeblood of any business and help achieve a competitive advantage in the workplace (Tieng et al., 2024 a; Win & Priyashantha, 2016). Retention refers to an organization's ability to maintain long-term relationships with employees, stakeholders, and clients. Human resource management (HRM) plays a key role in this process by keeping employees committed, engaged, and motivated, which prevents them from wanting to leave the organization (Asianab, 2023). It has been observed that leadership style significantly influences employee retention. Many employees are dissatisfied with their management's leadership, feel pressured at work, deal with ineffective leadership, lack motivation, and feel undervalued. These are key reasons why employees decide to leave the organization. To address these issues, we studied the impact of leadership styles on staff retention through case studies in public organizations in Battambang Province. Our research aimed to explore how leadership practices affect staff retention by investigating the effects of democratic, transformational, and passive leadership practices on staff retention; examining the perceptions of male and female civil servants or teachers regarding these three types of leadership; and examining staff perspectives on democratic, transformational, and passive leadership styles, as well as their impact on employee retention. This exploration provides a foundation for the next generation of scholars and for future research. Public entities can use these insights to enhance leadership training programs and improve organizational culture, offering practical knowledge to leaders for more effective approaches. By increasing employee satisfaction, loyalty, and commitment, this knowledge aids in decision-making and helps employees maximize their potential in the workplace more effectively.

Relationship between Democratic Leadership and Staff

Effective leadership is characterized by fostering relationships, promoting teamwork, and motivating employees within an organization, whereas management focuses on development, planning, and resource management. Consistent leadership behaviors play a crucial role in retaining employees, alongside management support. Research shows that effective leadership practices can increase productivity, job satisfaction, and adaptability in various situations. However, organizations face challenges with staff turnover due to increased competition and globalization. To recognize the importance of retention to maintain competitiveness and success, organizations must strive to prevent the loss of competent staff. Promoting employee engagement through effective leadership and management strategies is essential for long-term sustainability and organizational stability.

Democratic leadership is a style that strengthens employee involvement and influence in decision-making, encouraging discussion, debate, and collaboration. The principle of democratic leadership is to engage with other working groups, adopting collective action and joint decision-making (Bush, 2008). Democratic leaders support and promote the professional growth of employees. They delegate responsibilities, seek feedback from their teams, and use that information to drive decisions and implement new policies and procedures (Shinde, 2024). Democratic leaders demonstrate qualities such as honesty, courage, fairness, intelligence, and creativity, which help them build trust and gain the respect of their teams. This type of leadership can attract talented

individuals and reduce employee turnover by increasing job satisfaction and fostering a positive corporate culture (Stoyanov, 2022).

H1: Democratic leadership positively affects staff retention in the organization.

Relationship between Transformational Leadership and Staff

Transformational leadership, or change leadership, involves influencing significant changes in employees' attitudes, beliefs, values, organizational goals, and vision, enabling them to exceed expectations (Gomes, 2014). Transformational leadership identifies and reinforces attitudes that enhance employees' awareness of the importance and value of performance. It provides a vision for the future, a realistic action plan to achieve necessary goals, and individualized support to staff (Lindert et al., 2022). Gomes (2014) argues that transformational leaders have a guiding vision for employees and high expectations for their performance. They believe that employees have the ability and skills to improve. This type of leadership understands the needs of employees, promotes accountability, and fosters self-esteem, contributing to their personal growth.

H2: Transformational leadership positively affects staff retention in the organization.

The Relationship between Laissez-Faire Leadership and Staffing

According to Houlihan (2020), the laissez-faire leadership style encourages decision-making and gives employees the freedom to innovate, fostering creativity in problem solving. Laissez-faire leadership is characterized by minimal leader involvement in the work process, with little or no intervention in decision-making. Previous studies have often reported negative effects of laissez-faire leadership on employee behavior, leading to concerns about performance outcomes; however, a laissez-faire leader provides flexibility in work and decision-making authority, which can result in employees serving the organization longer and with greater integrity (Ali & Ullah, 2023).

Understanding Gender and Leadership Practices

Leadership practices refer to the methods that leaders use to provide guidance, implement plans, and motivate people to achieve goals (Northouse, 2018). In this context, democracy involves delegating power to employees, either directly or through their elected representatives (Merriam-Webster, 2024). According to Eagly et al. (2003), transformational leadership is often viewed positively by female employees because it incorporates guidance and personal development, aligning with gender roles in the community. Shondrick et al. (2010) suggest that laissez-faire leaders allow their followers the freedom to make decisions, which can increase employees' confidence in their efficiency. However, laissez-faire leadership is often characterized by a lack of direct oversight and reluctance to make decisions, which is generally viewed negatively by both male and female employees.

Civil Servants' Perceptions of Leadership

Both male and female civil servants tend to appreciate the transparency and fairness associated with democratic leadership, although women may find it particularly empowering owing to its emphasis on cooperation (Appelbaum et al., 2003). The differences between male and female civil servants' perceptions of transformational leadership are generally minimal, with both responding positively to this style of leadership because it emphasizes development and innovation (Eagly et al., 2003). Civil servants' perceptions of laissez-faire leadership are generally negative. The lack of involvement and guidance from laissez-faire leaders often leads to low morale, confusion, and reduced productivity. A study by Skogstad et al. (2007) highlighted that civil servants under laissez-faire leadership often show a lack of attention to work, which significantly affects their motivation and job satisfaction. Recruitment and retention in the public sector are closely linked to leadership practices. Effective leadership, particularly democratic and transformational styles, supports the creation of a positive work environment and fosters participation, which encourages employees to

remain with the organization (Griffeth et al., 2000; Tieng et al., 2024b; Tieng et al., 2024c). Leadership styles play important roles in implementing work and saving staff, increasing staff satisfaction and experiences, and increasing skills and capacity.

H3: Laissez-faire leadership positively affects staff retention in the organization.

Materials and Methods

Research Design

For this study, the researchers selected a quantitative research design to investigate the influence of leadership styles on five different public institutions: the National University of Battambang, Hun Sen Phnom Sampov High School, Battambang Provincial Department of Economy and Finance, Anlong Vil High School, and the Battambang Provincial Department of Tourism. The sample to be surveyed is selected via the simple random sampling method, which is based on a list of questions organized according to the defined number of samples.

Participants

The total number of samples for the study was 261, comprising staff and civil servants from the five public institutions in Battambang Province. This includes 75 staff members from the National University of Battambang, 55 staff members from Hun Sen Phnom Sampov High School, 103 staff members from Anlong Vil High School, 12 staff members from the Battambang Provincial Department of Tourism, and 17 staff members from the Battambang Provincial Department of Economy and Finance.

Instruments and Procedure

There were 40 items of questionnaires applied in this research study. Primary data were collected via questionnaires aligned with the research objectives, which targeted staff and civil servants at the five public institutions. Research materials for this study were sourced from the library of the National University of Battambang, including dissertations and other documents retrieved from the internet for a comprehensive literature review.

Data Analysis

The collected data were analyzed via Microsoft Excel and SPSS version 27, with a focus on quantitative analysis. The methods employed included means, standard deviations, and regressions.

Results

Influence of Leadership Style on Employee Retention

This study measured Cronbach's alpha of item reliability, t tests, and regressions. Table 1 presents the 40 items used to identify Democratic Leaders ($\alpha = 0.933$), Revolutionary Leaders ($\alpha = 0.797$), and Laissez-Faire Leaders ($\alpha = 0.931$). Employee retention had a Cronbach's alpha of 0.943. Hair et al. (1998), as cited by Tieng et al. (2024), reported that a Cronbach's $\alpha \geq 0.90$ is excellent, $0.90 > \alpha \geq 0.80$ is good, and $0.80 > \alpha \geq 0.70$ is acceptable. This result revealed that all 40 items are consistent with and reliable.

The hypothesis tests used t tests and regression analysis to evaluate the effects of democratic, transformational, and laissez-faire leadership on staff retention in Battambang's public sector. R² was used to measure the variance in the data explained by the regression line, with values ranging from 0 to 1.

- i. Democratic leadership: $\beta = 0.247$ and P value $< 0.05^{**}$, indicating a positive effect on staff retention. Hypothesis H1 is accepted.
- ii. Transformational leadership: $\beta = 0.901$ and P value $< 0.001^{***}$, indicating a strong positive effect on staff retention. Hypothesis H2 is accepted.
- iii. Laissez-Faire Leadership: $\beta = 0.165$ and P value $< 0.05^{**}$, suggesting a positive effect on staff retention. Hypothesis H3 is accepted.

Table 1. Cronbach's Alpha Values for Different Leadership Procedures

Factor	Items	Cronbach's Alpha
Democratic	Demo1>Dmo10	0.933
Transformational	Las1>Las10	0.797
Laissez-faire	Tran1>Tran10	0.931
Employee retention	Ret1>Ret10	0.943

Views on Leadership Variables by Gender

Table 2 presents the results of an independent samples test comparing male and female perceptions of democratic leadership. Among the 261 samples, 128 were male and 133 were female. The test revealed that perceptions of democratic leadership were similar for both genders, with a P value of 0.40, indicating nonsignificance ($T = 0.840$). The average score for women was 37.94, with a standard deviation of 6.787, whereas for men, it was 37.24, with a standard deviation of 6.622. Thus, both genders view democratic leadership similarly.

Table 2. Independent Samples Test for the Democratic Leadership Variables

Independent Samples Test							
Model Variable	Gender	N	M	SD	F	Sig.	t
Democratic	Female	133	37.94	6.787	.070	.040	.840
	Male	128	37.24	6.622			

Table 3 presents the results of the independent samples test comparing male and female perceptions of laissez-faire leadership. Among the 261 samples, 128 were male and 133 were female. The test revealed no significant difference in perceptions, with a P value of 0.56 ($T = -0.587$). The average score for women was 34.52, with a standard deviation of 5.052, whereas for men, it was 34.89, with a standard deviation of 5.176. Thus, both male and female civil servants have similar views on laissez-faire leadership.

Table 3. Independent Samples Test for the Laissez-Faire Leadership Variables

Independent Samples Test							
Model Variable	Gender	N	M	SD	F	Sig.	t
Laissez-faire	Female	133	34.52	5.052	.149	.56	-.587
	Male	128	34.89	5.176			

Table 4 presents the results of the independent samples test comparing male and female perceptions of transformational leadership. Among the 261 samples, 128 were male and 133 were female. The test revealed no significant difference in perceptions, with a P value of 0.45 ($T = 0.758$). The average score for women was 37.38, with a standard deviation of 6.864, whereas for men, it

was 36.75, with a standard deviation of 6.637. Therefore, both male and female civil servants have similar views on transformational leadership.

Table 4. Independent Samples Test for Transformational Leadership Variables

Independent Samples Test							
Model Variable	Gender	N	M	SD	F	Sig.	T
Transformational	Female	133	37.38	6.864	.008	.45	.758
	Male	128	36.75	6.637			.758

Table 5 displays the results of the independent samples test comparing male and female perceptions of the retention variables. Among the 261 samples, 128 were male and 133 were female. The test revealed no significant difference in perceptions, with a P value of 0.990 ($T = 0.012$). The average score for women was 38.66, with a standard deviation of 6.465, whereas for men, it was 38.65, with a standard deviation of 6.508. Thus, both male and female civil servants have similar views on retention, as shown in the following table.

Table 5. Independent Samples Test for Retention Variables

Independent Samples Test							
Model Variable	Gender	N	M	SD	F	Sig.	T
Transformational	Female	133	37.38	6.864	.008	.45	.758
	Male	128	36.75	6.637			.758

Employees' Perceptions of Leadership Styles and Retention

Democratic Leadership Variability

The survey results show that perceptions of democratic leadership vary, with average scores ranging from $M = 3.49$ to $M = 3.92$ and standard deviations from $SD = 0.947$ to $SD = 0.826$. Employees expressed confidence in their leaders with a higher average score ($M = 3.92$, $SD = 0.826$). However, they were less positive about transparency and accountability in decision-making ($M = 3.49$, $SD = 0.947$). This suggests that while employees generally trust their leaders, there is a need for improved transparency and accountability in decision-making processes in Battambang's public units.

Laissez-Faire Leadership Variability

Perceptions of laissez-faire leadership ranged from $M = 2.83$ to $M = 3.80$, with standard deviations from $SD = 1.047$ to $SD = 0.742$. Employees appreciated receiving feedback on their work ($M = 3.80$, $SD = 0.742$) but were dissatisfied with the lack of guidance provided by leaders ($M = 2.83$, $SD = 0.742$). This indicates a need for increased guidance and support from leaders in Battambang's public units.

Transformational leadership variability

Transformational leadership perceptions had average scores ranging from $M = 3.36$ to $M = 3.89$ and standard deviations ranging from $SD = 0.968$ to $SD = 0.861$. Employees valued leaders who supported their development ($M = 3.89$, $SD = 0.861$) but were less satisfied with leaders who allowed too much freedom in how work was done ($M = 3.36$, $SD = 0.968$). Public units in Battambang should focus on balancing support with structured guidance to improve employee satisfaction.

Employee Retention

Retention perceptions ranged from $M = 3.66$ to $M = 4.02$, with standard deviations from $SD = 0.842$ to $SD = 0.744$. Employees found their work meaningful ($M = 4.02$, $SD = 0.744$) but were less satisfied with the benefits provided ($M = 3.66$, $SD = 0.842$). This suggests a need for public units in Battambang to enhance benefits and rewards to better retain staff.

Discussion

The Impact of Leadership Styles on Employee Retention

The analysis shows that democratic leadership has a $\beta = 0.247$ and a P value <0.05 , indicating a significant positive effect on staff retention. This finding supports Hypothesis H1, affirming that democratic leadership enhances staff retention in public entities. This finding aligns with Gastil's (1994) research, which highlights that democratic leadership improves employee satisfaction and commitment by involving them in decision-making. This approach is similar to Ronald's (2016) democratic leadership style, which is best for implementing and saving staff and has a 99% satisfaction rate. This leadership style results in positive responses from civil servants in working as well as work satisfaction.

Thus, transformational leadership had a $\beta = 0.901$ and a P value <0.001 , indicating a very positive effect on staff retention. The adoption of Hypothesis H2 confirms the strong positive impact of transformational leadership on retention. This result is consistent with Bass and Avolio's (1994) study, which revealed that transformational leaders inspire and motivate employees, leading to greater job satisfaction and commitment. Similarly, Muynihan (2021) reported that this leadership style positively saves staff and employees and helps them gain their capacity growth experience at work. Overall, the transformational leadership style certainly has a positive effect on maintaining staff.

Compared with democratic and transformational leadership, laissez-faire leadership had a $\beta = 0.165$ and a P value <0.05 , indicating a significant but lesser effect on staff retention. Hypothesis H3 is supported, suggesting that laissez-faire leadership has a positive effect on retention, although to a lesser degree. This finding is in line with that of Skogstad et al. (2007), who noted that while excessive laissez-faire leadership can cause dissatisfaction, a moderate level provides autonomy and can positively influence retention.

Gender Perceptions of Leadership Styles

The analysis revealed no significant gender differences in perceptions of democratic leadership ($T = 0.840$, $P = 0.40$). Women had an average score of $M = 37.94$ ($SD = 6.787$), and men had an average score of $M = 37.24$ ($SD = 6.622$). This finding is consistent with Eagly and Johannesen-Schmidt (2001), who reported that both men and women value democratic leadership similarly.

Similarly, perceptions of transformational leadership showed no significant gender differences ($T = 0.758$, $P = 0.56$). Women scored an average of $M = 37.38$ ($SD = 6.864$), whereas men scored $M = 36.75$ ($SD = 6.637$). This result aligns with Bass and Avolio (1994), who reported that transformational leadership traits are equally appreciated by both genders.

For laissez-faire leadership, the difference between men and women was also nonsignificant ($T = -0.587$, $P = 0.45$). Women had an average score of $M = 34.52$ ($SD = 5.052$), and men had $M = 34.89$ ($SD = 5.176$). This finding is consistent with Avolio et al. (1999), who reported that laissez-faire leadership is generally viewed similarly by both sexes, often negatively because of its lack of guidance and support.

Views of Civil Servants on Leadership Practices

Studies show that the democratic leadership variables have an average score ranging from $M = 3.49$ to $M = 3.92$, with a standard deviation between $SD = 0.947$ and $SD = 0.826$. Civil servants generally have a positive view of democratic leadership, particularly in terms of trust and satisfaction with their leaders ($M = 3.92$, $SD = 0.826$). This finding aligns with Gastil's (1994) study, which suggests that democratic leadership often results in higher employee satisfaction due to increased participation in decision-making.

The stability of transformational leadership has an average score from $M = 3.36$ to $M = 3.89$, with a standard deviation ranging from $SD = 0.968$ to $SD = 0.861$. Employees have a positive view of leaders who help them develop ($M = 3.89$, $SD = 0.861$) and provide job-related guidance ($M = 3.88$, $SD = 0.680$). These results are consistent with Bass and Riggio's (2006) findings that transformational leaders inspire and develop their followers, leading to higher job satisfaction and performance. However, the lowest score was for allowing employees to work as they wished ($M = 3.36$, $SD = 0.968$), indicating some dissatisfaction with this aspect of leadership.

Laissez-faire leadership had an average score ranging from $M = 2.83$ to $M = 3.80$, with standard deviations from $SD = 1.047$ to $SD = 0.742$. Employees have a positive attitude toward receiving feedback and resources from their leaders ($M = 3.80$, $SD = 0.742$), which is consistent with Skogstad et al.'s (2007) findings that laissez-faire leadership can provide necessary support and resources. This result is also closely related to Hinkin and Schriesheim (2008), who reported that laissez-faire often professed negative responses due to passive guidance and support from leaders, which led to low work satisfaction. Therefore, public entities in Battambang city should consider providing more reliable guidance and support to civil servants, staff, and officials effectively.

Conclusion

The findings of this study showed considerable similarities with those of previous research, even though the studies were conducted in different cultural contexts and organizational settings. The results indicated that democratic and revolutionary leadership styles positively affect staff retention in public organizations in Battambang Province. The staff and officials in Battambang Province are satisfied with working with and leading their leaders, and they actively participate in every activity led by their leaders. Thus, staff and officials had more chances to improve their skills and capacities through these leadership styles. In contrast, laissez-faire leadership tends to have negative effects on this conduct. The staff and officials seem unsatisfied with the styles led by their leaders, as they rarely receive support from their leaders during work progress. In short, Democratic and transformational leaders have positive impacts on people around the workplace, and these impacts make employees, employers, officials, and staff satisfied with their current work.

Recommendation

This study is as follows:

- i. Civil Servants: Encourage open communication, allowing staff to express concerns and suggestions without fear of retaliation. A robust feedback system should be implemented to ensure transparency and accountability.
- ii. For organizations: Develop leadership training programs that focus on ethical, transparent, and accountable practices. Staff should be empowered by delegating authority and supporting innovation.

iii. For Society: Promotion of openness and accountability in leadership decisions to build public trust. Encourage leaders to provide freedom to employees while maintaining support for key objectives.

iv. For future researchers, additional variables and diverse methods, sample sizes, and locations should be explored to better understand leadership influences in various contexts. Further research should investigate how leadership styles affect other factors in public entities in Cambodia.

Acknowledgment

We, the 17th Bachelor of Business Administration cohort in the 2020-2024 academic year from the Faculty of Business Management and Tourism at the National University of Battambang, sincerely extend our gratitude to the following:

Our parents, who have worked tirelessly to raise, care for, and nurture us from infancy, guiding us toward education and the right path in life. His Excellency Sok Khorn, Rector of the National University of Battambang, for his dedication to reforming the university's educational standards, elevating them to the national and international levels. Dr. Sam Rany, our main supervisor, who provided invaluable guidance in data analysis, helped make this research successful. Ms. Soeun Chenda, our supervisor, contributed valuable ideas that significantly improved this thesis. The director of the Battambang Provincial Department of Tourism, the director of the Battambang Provincial Department of Economy and Finance, the director of Hun Sen Phnom Sampov High School, and the director of Anlong Vil High School permitted us to collect data in these study areas. Ms. Soeng Pov Ratanamony, an employee at the Department of Economy and Finance, facilitated our data collection efforts at the Department of Economy and Finance, Battambang Province.

Mr. Nara, Administrative Officer at Hun Sen Phnom Sampov High School, assisted us with data collection at Hun Sen Phnom Sampov High School. In return, we raise our hands in deep respect and gratitude to His Excellency, the Rector of the National University of Battambang, and wish him abundant energy, strength, longevity, and the fulfillment of all his aspirations.

Conflict of Interest

There are no conflicts of interest.

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